

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Abagoami****FIRST NAME: Innocent****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX (6)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: FUNDAMENTALS OF INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1. **What does it take to write a good academic essay?**

- Writing down everything you know about a topic.
- Analysing, then answering the essay's question or task.
- Being sure that you understand exactly what the question requires you to do while Identifying the key words and clarifying the approach you intend to use.
- All the above mentioned.**¹

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Karibu Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University), 11.

2. **Writing someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author or having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor could be termed:**

- Plagiarism.²**
- Coping.
- In-text citation.
- Appreciating the work of others.

3. **How are acronyms used for the first time in a text?**

- This is done by placing the acronym or its source phrase in parentheses, and thereafter using just the acronym.³**
- This is done by talking about the acronym.
- The acronym should be spelt out each time.
- The acronym should be explained every time it's being used.

4. **Quotations must be placed in quotation marks or indented as a block quote. All quotations must include a citation, a note or parenthetical citation, referring the reader to the source document. Which of the following changes are not permitted in quotations?**

- Adding brackets to indicate material or emphasis added to a quote.
- Adding Italics to add emphasis to words or phrases within a quotation, or to the entire quotation.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Karibu Gulma, 15.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Karibu Gulma, 44.

Quoting material in a foreign language and reproducing all accents and other marks exactly as they appear in the original.

All the above mentioned.⁴

5. **For general matters of spelling, Chicago recommends using Webster's Third New International Dictionary and its chief abridgment, Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary . . . in its latest edition. If more than one spelling is given, or more than one form of the plural . . .**

Chicago expects you to use any dictionary at your disposal.

Look for the nearest synonym (s).

Chicago normally opts for the first form listed, thus aiding consistency. If, as occasionally happens, the Collegiate disagrees with the Third International, the Collegiate should be followed, since it represents the latest lexical research.⁵

Abandon all the possible spellings given.

6. **Readers expect experienced researcher to ask and answer different kinds of questions. What are these questions?**

Conceptual questions.

Practical questions.

Applied questions.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Karibu Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University), 148.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Karibu Gulma, 44.

All the above mentioned.⁶

7. **Depending on your experience, readers will expect you to use different levels of sources for your dissertation or thesis. These are:**

Primary Sources for Evidence.

Secondary Sources to Learn from Other Researchers.

Tertiary Sources for Introductory Overviews.

All the above mentioned.⁷

8. **Different fields seem to introduce reports in different ways, but behind most of them is a pattern containing the following:**

Opening context or background.

A statement of your research question.

The significance of your question as well as claim.

All the above mentioned.⁸

9. **The review of related literature involves the systematic identification, location, and analysis of material related to the research problem. This material includes:**

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16-17.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, 24-25.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 70.

- Books, book chapters, articles, abstracts, reviews, monographs, dissertations, research reports, and electronic media.**⁹
- Role and scope of artists.
- Specialized research work.
- Thoughts of Conservatives.

10. **The *acquis* is the body of EU law in the broad sense, comprising:**

- Primary legislation and secondary legislations, the case law of the Court of Justice as well as declarations and resolutions adopted by the Union.
- measures relating to the common foreign and security policy and justice and home affairs.
- international agreements concluded by the Union and those concluded by the Member States among themselves in connection with the Union's activities.
- All the above mentioned.**¹⁰

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning To End* (California: Sage Publications, Inc., 2008), 46.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (Luxembourg: European Commission, 2011), 51.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.